

AI INFLUENCE ON TEACHER-STUDENT RELATIONSHIPS AND EDUCATIONAL ETHICS

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Abstract: This research article aims to examine both teachers' and students' attitudes and perceptions of the integration of AI in the educational sphere, ESP courses in particular, concerning privacy, bias, and the evolving nature of the teacher-student relationship. With the mini-research conducted at Fergana State University, the results of this study state that, whereas educators and students recognize AI's potential to develop learning, concerns about privacy, bias, and the changing roles of teachers and students highlight the need for ethical guidelines to ensure responsible and transparent AI integration in education.

Аннотация: Эта исследовательская статья направлена на изучение как отношения, так и восприятия преподавателей и студентов по поводу интеграции ИИ в образовательную сферу, в частности, в курсы английского языка для специальных целей (ESP), с акцентом на вопросы конфиденциальности, предвзятости и изменяющуюся природу отношений между преподавателями и студентами. Результаты мини-исследования, проведенного в Ферганском государственном университете, показывают, что, несмотря на то, что Educators and students recognize the potential of AI to enhance

learning, concerns regarding privacy, bias, and the evolving roles of teachers and students underscore the need for ethical guidelines to ensure responsible and transparent integration of AI in education.

Key words: AI, education, privacy, bias, ethical guidelines

Ключевые слова: ИИ, образование, конфиденциальность, предвзятость, этические рекомендации

1. Introduction

The use of AI in learning environments has over the recent past received an encouraging uptake, adopting new teaching methodologies in the classroom. In recent years, intelligent tutoring systems, personalized learning contexts, and data analysis technologies have been constituents of AI in learning systems. Promises associated with this technology include increased student attention, improved learning an education delivery system that fits specific students. This ethos increases the potential of the manifestation of AI as the inherent innovative creations of educators, and institutions to transform education.

However, together with such great potential advantages that have been forecasted, many urgent ethical concerns that should be discussed. Leveraging AI in education presents some interesting questions of privacy since every data collected and utilized across the learning process will sooner or later result in a violation of privacy and misuse of information. Also, one external threat is an algorithmic bias that escalates the likelihood of making a biased decision about providing education and increasing prejudice in educational attainment. In addition, many factors resulting from an AI-driven environment may influence the relationships between a teacher and a learner, as the use of technological tools affects interpersonal communication within a classroom and outside of it.

The aim of this article is to investigate the social nature of ethical issues about AI in; this view, with a focus on; privacy concerns; biases, and; the blurring of the teacher-student relationship. Through the analysis of these aspects, the intention is to make the practice of using AI technologies in education more understandable and

to stimulate the right organisational actions that respond to the importance of ethical approaches and the need to create a non-discriminatory learning environment for students.

2. Literature review

Reiss and White [6, p. 3] writing on the subject suggest that education should aim at the well-being of human beings. To succeed, this concept transcends the assimilation of information and knowledge to produce meaningful, constructive members of society. To achieve this broader aim, the article increase the understanding of social policy in a way that is particularly useful today, given the existing and growing environmental consequences of human behaviors. Although recognizing the role of powerful knowledge in the educational process [8, p. 2], Reiss [5, p. 2] notes that people's well-being is a better goal for learning. It is the process of enabling people to perform purposes, tasks, and other roles in their lives within given relationships, activities, and experiences in ways that are most personally meaningful and enriching to the individual.

The principles of well-being date back to ethical philosophy; Aristotle's *Nicomachean Ethics* and *Politics*. However, the question of what kind of life is good or worthy remains incredibly vague. Yet some people, such as the utilitarians or Bentham's hedonists, associate it with pleasure and the absence of pain, while others associate it with money, fame, or the fulfillment of all needs. The question is how to define prosperity so that it is more profound than what it might seem at first glance when all the elements of a rich and meaningful life are considered. This is very important to understand because satisfying desires can have consequences that are not constructive and institutionally responsible.

As Rane, et al. and Sajja [3, p. 2; 7, p. 4] state in their research words, according to their point of views, AI is revolutionizing education in providing new tools to improve learning, simplify administrative work, and tailor lessons to individual students' needs. However, supporting this view, Eden et al. [2, p. 3] argue that while AI has the potential to revolutionise education, several challenges need to be overcome for its successful implementation, paying attention to the main

obstacles, including limited access to AI resources, concerns about privacy and security of student data, widening digital divide and the potential for bias against AI algorithms.

Aghaziarati et al. [1, pp. 36-37] examined their research among the target group comprised 25 teachers from primary, secondary, and tertiary institutions who had prior experience with AI tools in their teaching practices. This diverse group represented a range of subjects, teaching experience levels, and technological proficiency, providing a broad perspective on AI integration in education [1, p. 37]. The study, involving 25 educators with diverse backgrounds and experience levels, identified four key themes related to teachers' attitudes towards AI in education: pedagogical impacts, ethical and social considerations, technological challenges and opportunities, and perceptions of AI in education.

In the results, they stated that their study revealed both the potential and challenges of integrating AI into education [1, p. 38]. Teachers emphasized the benefits of AI for personalized learning, immediate feedback, and engagement, but also highlighted the need for AI literacy, interdisciplinary teaching, and careful curriculum integration. They acknowledged the evolving teacher role from knowledge provider to learning facilitator and emphasized the need for ethical and effective AI tool usage. Automated assessment tools were seen as beneficial but raised concerns about bias and fairness. Technological infrastructure and teacher training emerged as significant barriers to wider AI implementation [1, pp. 38-39].

3. Methods

As the main research aim of this paper is to investigate the social nature of ethical issues about AI while focusing on privacy concerns, biases, and the blurring of the teacher-student relationship, the focus group discussion was used. The main research question of this study is: “How do educators perceive and experience the ethical challenges posed by AI in education, specifically concerning privacy, bias, and the evolving nature of the teacher-student relationship?”. This interview consisted of 4 personal open-ended questions.

3.1. Participants' demographic

Two target groups participated in this survey. Both professors with at least 10 years of teaching experience along with the senior students took part in this research. This focus group discussion was anonymous, and any personal information was omitted. The overall gender distribution from both of the groups is 58.5% female and 41.5% males.

3.1.1. Teachers' demographic

Two professors, representing both of the genders, submitted their responses. Teacher 1 has studied in UK and has more diverse answers for the main research question, while Teacher 2 has more teaching year experience.

3.1.2. Students' demographic

There were 3 senior students majoring in English philology at Fergana State University. The gender of the participants is 67% and 33% for females and males respectively. The average age range is 23 years old.

4. Results

4.1. Teachers' perception of AI integration

4.1.1. The first question: "How do you feel AI tools have changed the way teachers and students interact with each other?"

Teacher 1: "AI tools make communication faster, which encourages students to talk more in class."

Teacher 2: "AI can be helpful with tasks, but it sometimes reduces face-to-face communication."

Teachers disagree on the impact of AI tools. Teacher 1 believes AI makes communication faster, leading to more student participation. Teacher 2 thinks AI helps with tasks but might decrease direct interaction.

4.1.2. Second question: "Can you share an experience where you felt your privacy was at risk due to AI in education?"

Teacher 1: "I was worried when an AI system shared student data without permission. We need to be careful about how much information is being shared."

Teacher 2: "One of my students worried about an AI tool tracking their progress. It made them feel uncomfortable."

Both teachers expressed concerns about AI in education potentially compromising student privacy. Teacher 1 was worried about unauthorized data sharing, while Teacher 2 noted a student's discomfort with being tracked by an AI tool.

4.1.3. Third question: “In what ways do you think bias in AI affects the learning experience for students?”

Teacher 1: “If AI favors certain learning styles, it could be unfair to students who learn differently.”

Teacher 2: “AI bias can make students feel less confident if it misjudges their abilities.”

Both teachers point out how AI bias can be harmful to students. Teacher 1 says it can unfairly favor some learning styles, while Teacher 2 says it can make students feel bad by misjudging them.

4.1.4. Fourth question: “What ethical concerns do you think are most important when using AI in the classroom?”

Teacher 1: “Transparency is key. Students and teachers need to know how AI works and what data it uses to make sure learning is fair.”

Teacher 2: “The biggest concern is how student data is used. We need to make sure AI protects student privacy and is used responsibly.”

Both teachers agree that using AI in the classroom raises important ethical issues, mainly about being transparent with students and teachers about how it works, and protecting student privacy.

4.2. Students' perception of AI integration

4.2.1. Perception regardless of AI's impact on interaction

AI tools have fundamentally changed the dynamic between teachers and students by enabling more immediate and efficient communication. They allow for quick feedback from teachers, making learning more interactive and allowing students to get help easily. These tools also facilitate faster clarification of concepts by enabling real-time discussions with teachers, making learning more effective and less frustrating.

4.2.2. Perception regardless of privacy concerns

The answers highlight a common concern about AI in education: the potential for privacy violations. All three respondents felt uncomfortable with AI tracking their study habits, monitoring their assignments, and collecting their test results. They expressed concern about the lack of transparency regarding data usage and who had access to their personal information, raising valid points about the need for clear ethical guidelines and user consent in AI-powered educational tools.

4.2.3. Perception regardless of bias in learning

Bias in AI can negatively affect students' learning experiences in several ways. If an AI tool prefers certain writing styles, students with different approaches may feel unsupported. Additionally, if the AI overlooks diverse perspectives in literature, important voices and ideas might be missed, limiting students' understanding. When AI does not take into account various backgrounds, it may fail to address the unique learning needs of all students, making it harder for everyone to succeed. Bias in AI can create an unfair learning environment.

4.2.4. Perception regardless of ethics in classrooms

When using AI in the classroom, several important ethical concerns arise. First, privacy is crucial; it's essential to protect students' personal information to ensure their safety. Second, the accuracy of AI tools is vital because mistakes can lead to unfair grading and impact students' learning experiences negatively. Lastly, transparency is important; students should know how AI operates and how it uses their data, so they can feel secure and informed about the technology being used in their education.

5. Discussion

5.1. Teachers' analysis

The research on the sociological perspective regarding privacy, bias, and the influence of AI on teacher-student relationships reveals significant ethical challenges that educators face. Both professors, despite their differing backgrounds and experiences, highlight critical concerns surrounding the integration of AI in education. They express conflicting views on how AI tools affect communication—

one sees increased student participation while the other worries about diminished personal interaction. Privacy emerges as a common theme, with concerns about unauthorized data sharing and the discomfort students feel when monitored by AI. Additionally, both educators recognize the detrimental impact of AI bias on student confidence and learning opportunities, emphasizing that AI systems must be designed to support diverse learning styles. The consensus on the importance of transparency and responsible data usage underscores the need for ethical guidelines in AI implementation, ensuring that both students and teachers are informed and protected in this evolving educational landscape.

5.2. Student' analysis

The study identifies major issues students have with AI in learning, particularly on the issues of privacy, bias, and ethical issues. Students like new possibilities that AI provides for transferring messages between them and their teachers, as well as new opportunities in making the process of learning more engaging, but at the same they are uncomfortable with AI monitoring their activities and gathering personal information insincerely. They also find AI bias because the system promotes specific approaches to writing while excluding other views and approaches. In sum, students stress appreciating ethical codes and regulations about their privacy, completeness, and openness of the ways their data have been used in learning involving or relating to AI technologies.

6. Conclusion

Therefore, based on the surveys among educators and students, the ethical implications of using AI for,,: for Privacy, bias and the changing roles of the teachers and students in the classroom display a raised ethical question mark. Professionals agree that AI can increase the effectively of communication and interest, yet, they pose challenges of lack of contact, and leakage of data to third parties. Students however see AI as providing interactive chances for learning although they are a bit uncomfortable with what it means by monitoring and that AI systems have inherent bias in what and who they choose to overlook when it comes to learning styles. Both groups single out the growing demand of ethical rules for the AI application that

helps to make proper usage of educational data transparent and protect students from the potential risks in deeper integration of AI technologies into the learning process. It is, therefore, imperative to discuss these ethical issues to enhance trust and optimise on the use of AI in education.

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